

UDC: 633.18/631.17.

THE EFFECT OF WATER NORMS ON THE DEVELOPMENTAL PHASES OF A MEDIUM-RIPE RICE (ORIZA SATIVA) VARIETY

¹Khojamkulova Yulduzoy Jakhonkulovna, ²Asraev Usman Nasirovich

¹Rice Research Institute Head of the Laboratory of Physiology and Biochemistry of Plants
Doctor of Philosophy in Agricultural Sciences senior researcher, ²senior lecturer of TDAU
"General zootechnics and veterinary" department, candidate of agricultural sciences

¹ORCID:<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4694-7324>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13848023>

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада ўртапишар “Искандар” шולי навида 5; 10; 15 ва 20 см ли сув қалинлигида ўсимликнинг ўсиши, ривожланиши фазаларидаги сувга бўлган маълумотлар ёритилган.

Калим сўзлар: Шולי, меъёр, сугориши сарфи м³, агротехник тадбир, ҳосилдорлик.

Аннотация. В данной статье Освещены данные о росте растений, фазах развития при 5; 10; 15 и 20 см слоя воды на примере риса сорта «Искандар» средние спелости.

Ключевые слова: Рис, норма, поливной расход м³, агротехнические мероприятия, урожайность.

Abstract. This article highlights data on plant growth, development phases at 5 10 15 and 20 cm of water layer on the example of rice variety "Iskandar" of medium ripeness.

Keywords: Rice, norm, watering consumption м³, agrotechnical measures, productivity.

Relevance of the topic: Given that the development of rice is an urgent task, in recent years, serious attention has been paid to this area, that is, efforts are being made to balance the extensive and intensive paths of development. In order to form a single system of rice cultivation and procurement, rational use of land and water resources, as well as to fill the domestic consumer market with high quality products According to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2021 No PR-4973 "On measures to further develop rice cultivation" Wide application of water-saving technologies in rice cultivation, planting of 20% of rice fields by seedlings, introduction of laser leveling system in 50%, sowing of rice seeds in modern seeders in 30% is set as a task[1].

The degree of study of the subject: According to the research of foreign scientists S.Khan and R.Tariq (rice germination, accumulation, flowering, phases and influencing the growth and development of the plant), rice is one of the most important components in the world for cultivation, because when water-saving irrigation regimes are used for rice than in all other crops in agriculture, and based on different experimental results Irrigation depth level is one of the most important problems that we need to solve at a time when 6-8 thousand cubic meters per hectare is used for rice cultivation in countries such as China, Japan and Korea wich are rice producing countries we spend 3 times more water then they do [2]. In the scientific research of M.J.Norman and C.J.Pearson, rice also develops underwater conditions due to aerenchyma cells that allow air to pass through the leaves to the roots. Approximately 34 to 43 percent of the world's irrigation water, or 24 to 30 percent of the world's available fresh water, has been shown to be effective in sowing seeds up to 1 cm deep in 10 cm of water. When rice was constantly irrigated at a level of 5-15 cm, it was observed that 900 м³ of water was used per hectare when the water was discharged once, ie 25.1 м³ when the water was not drained, and 26.0 thousand м³ when it was drained [3].

The aim of the study: In the rice fields, the medium-ripe Iskandar rice variety (*oriza sativa*) was grown, and in the developmental stages, the effect of different water depth level (Iskandar, 18500 m³), water consumption, m³ was determined.

Research methods: "Methods of conducting field experiments" [5], "Methods of field experiments" [4]. (B.A.Dospekhov. 1973) and "Methodological guidelines for water conservation in rice cultivation in Uzbekistan (2019)".

Research results: When studying the amount of water used by rice during the growing season, water depth level of 5, 10, 15 and 20 cm (per hectare) on the example of the medium-ripe rice variety "Iskandar" (*oriza sativa*) in the rice fields of the experimental field of the Rice Research Institute we observed 13700 m³ with a level of 5 cm, 17600 m³ with a level of 10 cm, 19,700 m³ with a level of 15 cm and 20,800 m³ with a level of 20 cm, (high concentration and water saving in 15 cm variant) 1870 m³ during germination, 2050 m³ during weeding, 2400 m³ during accumulation, 2770 m³ during tubing, 3830 m³ during germination, 4860 m³ during flowering and 1920 m³ during general ripening water consumption was 19,700 m³.

CONCLUSIONS AND PROPOSALS

1. From the data obtained, it can be concluded that with water depth level increases (5,10,15 and 20 cm), the longer growth period of rice varieties is observed. (With an increase in water level of more than 20 cm, the studied varieties increased the number of empty grains in the stalk, and the increased tendency of the stem to lie down led to a decrease in yield).

A study of the amount of water discharged from rice-grown checks during the season shows that when the water level at the border is 5 cm, 13-15% (relative to seasonal irrigation) and 18–22% in other options.

The results of experiments on rice irrigation showed that the variation of water thickness at the boundary had an impact on the discharge to the general irrigation norm and on the growth, development and yield of rice varieties.

In order to grow high-quality rice and high economic efficiency in the conditions of grasslands and swamps of Tashkent region, it is recommended to irrigate the medium-ripe rice variety "Iskandar" at a depth level of 15 cm on the basis of recommended agro-technical measures.

REFERENCES

1. A.A.Nurmatov, B.D.Allashov, Sh.Sh.Jabborov, I.Rustamova, Sh.Tursunov. Feeding farm animals based on the new innovative total mixed ration (TMR) technology. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 2020/12/1. 614 (1), 012161 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012161>
2. B.Amanturdiev, B.Allashov, F.Toreev, N.Khudoyberdiev, U.Beknaev. Investigating stimulated ripening indicators of longbeak rattlebox (*Crotalaria*) planted in the coasts of the Aral Sea. E3S Web of Conferences, 2023, 421, 01001. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202342101001>
3. B.D.Allashov, M.X.Zulfikarov, F.Toreev. Effective agrotechnology for cultivation of forage crops. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 614 (1), 012159 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012159>
4. B.D.Allashov, M.X.Zulfikarov, F.Toreev. Effective agrotechnology for cultivation of forage crops. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 614 (1), 012159

5. B.D.Allashov, M.X.Zulfikarov, M.N.Sattarov. Primary seed production of fodder crops. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 614 (1), 012160 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012160>
6. B.Mardatov, B.Allashev, U.Beknaev, R.Khalimmetova, A.Sharapov. Mixed cultivation of legumes and cereals to strengthen the fodder base in cattle husbandry. E3S Web of Conferences, 2021, 258, 04048
7. Dospekhov.B.A. "Methods of field opyta" Moscow "Kolos" 1973. 227-248.
8. Khan.S & Tariq.R. Can irrigation be sustainable? Agricultural Water Management. 80 (1): 2006. p. 87- 99.
9. M.I.Annaveva, F.N.Toreev, M.M.Yakubov, B.D.Allashov, N. Mavlonova. Agrotechnology of Melilotus albus cultivation in saline area. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science 614 (1), 012170 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012170>
10. Norman.M.J. & Pearson.C.J. Tropical Food Crops in their Environment (2 nd ed.). Cambridge University Press: 2009. p. 3-5.
11. Nurmarov A.A., Allashov B.D., Yunusov B., Jabborov S.S. The influence of natural biologically active additives on the growth and development of stallions of the Karabair breed. IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 2020, 614(1), 012162 <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1755-1315/614/1/012162>
12. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan February 2, 2021 № PR-4973. On measures to further develop rice cultivation.
13. Sh.Nurmatov, K.Mirzajonov (2007) “Methods of conducting field experiments” [pp. 8-51].